

Material Properties of the Tectorial Membrane in Ceacam Mutant Mice

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ABSTRACT

CEACAM16 is a major constituent of the mammalian tectorial membrane (TM) and loss of CEACAM16 leads to progressive changes in TM structure (Cheatham *et al.*, 2014), so that a clearly defined striated sheet matrix fails to develop and holes with dimensions of tens of micrometers are observed, especially in the apical regions of the cochlea. Except for the increased incidence of spontaneous otoacoustic emissions, cochlear function is near-normal in *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} juveniles at 1 month of age, but distortion product otoacoustic emission (DPOAE) magnitudes decrease at older ages (\sim 7 months) when compared to wild-type mice (Goodyear *et al.*, 2019). To investigate how loss of CEACAM16 affects material properties of the TM, we previously measured wave properties of TMs isolated from both wild-type mice and CEACAM16 functional nulls (*Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal}). Here we compare those results with new point measurements obtained with a vibrating microsphere that probes mechanics at spatial scales on the order of single hair bundles.

FIGURE 1. Left: Comparison of DPOAE thresholds for *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} and *Ceacam16*^{+/+} mice (both at an age of 7 months). The levels of f_1 and f_2 were equal at 70 dB SPL. Dots show the median thresholds for 7 *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} mice (black) and 10 wild-type mice (red), and the verticals indicate standard errors in the mean. Adapted from Goodyear *et al.* (2019). Right: Histological section of 20 kHz region of a TM from an adult (P43) *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} mouse, illustrating large holes (white) in the TM. Adapted from Cheatham *et al.* (2014).

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BACKGROUND

Wave measurements of TMs from Ceacam mutant and wild-type mice. To investigate how loss of CEACAM16 affects the TM, we previously measured wave properties of TMs isolated from both wild-type (*Ceacam16^{+/+}*) mice and CEACAM16 functional nulls (*Ceacam16^{βgal/βgal}*) that were either young (4-6 weeks of age) or old (12-14 weeks of age). Median wave speeds were generally slower for adult *Ceacam16^{βgal/βgal}* TMs (4.55 m/s) than for wild-type TMs (5.88 m/s) and this result was highly statistically significant ($p < 10^{-6}$). Similarly, decay constants for adult *Ceacam16^{βgal/βgal}* TMs (94 μm) were generally smaller than those for wild-type TMs (196 μm) and this result was also highly statistically significant ($p < 10^{-6}$).

We analyzed a model of the TM to estimate TM material properties from the measured wave parameters. The median value of normalized shear viscosity of adult *Ceacam16^{βgal/βgal}* TMs (median: 1.90 (μm)²) is smaller than that of wild-type TMs by a factor of 1.8. The median value of normalized shear modulus for adult *Ceacam16^{βgal/βgal}* TMs (median: 1.11 (μm)²) is more than three times smaller than that for wild-type TMs.

In summary, both the normalized shear moduli and shear viscosities of adult *Ceacam16^{βgal/βgal}* TMs tend to be smaller than those of wild-type TMs.

FIGURE 2. Wave and corresponding material properties for wild-type (50 measurements from 6 preparations) and *Ceacam16^{βgal/βgal}* (49 measurements from 5 preparations) TMs. All TMs were taken from the mid-apical region of the cochlea, and results for frequencies from 10 to 15 kHz were pooled. Crosses indicate median values. Horizontal and vertical extents indicate interquartile ranges. Shear viscosity η was normalized by dividing by the product of density times radian frequency. Shear modulus G' was normalized by dividing by the product of density times radian frequency square. Adapted from Mansour et al. (2021).

Poroelastic properties of the TM. The TM is a polyelectrolyte gel that consists of a matrix of relatively non-diffusible macromolecules with ionizable charge groups, mobile (diffusible) ions, and water, all in contact with an aqueous bath (Freeman *et al.*, 2003). Mechanical properties of such gels depend on forces that arise in the matrix as well as forces that result from the flow of water through the matrix. Hydrodynamic coupling between the matrix and interstitial fluid depends critically on the size of the effective pores in the matrix through which the interstitial fluid can flow. Differences in the size of pores have been shown to account for differences in material properties of the TMs from mice with genetically modified TMs (Sellon *et al.*, 2014).

Dynamic nano-indentation measurements of the TM. Recent measurements of TM material properties using an AFM cantilever with vibrating microsphere tip have demonstrated that TM dynamic mechanical properties depend critically on the size of the measurement probe (Sellon *et al.*, 2019). Motions of a probe with dimensions on the order of a hair bundle are resisted by frequency-dependent forces that are in phase with TM displacement at low and high frequencies, but are in phase with TM velocity at transition frequencies (Sellon *et al.*, 2019). The resulting phase lead can be as much as a quarter of a cycle, and can thereby contribute significantly to cochlear mechanics.

In this manuscript, we report dynamic nano-indentation measurements of material properties of *Ceacam16^{βgal/βgal}* and wild-type TMs, and we compare those results to previously reported wave measurements of TMs from these same mouse lines.

METHODS

TMs from *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} and wild-type mice were isolated from the surrounding tissue and attached with a tissue adhesive (Cell-Tak) to a small rectangle of glass cut from a coverslip. A microsphere was attached to an AFM cantilever so that it could be brought into contact with the TM and then indented into the TM using a piezoelectric crystal (Figure 3 left). A static displacement ($\delta_0 = 0.1 - 0.4 \mu\text{m}$) was applied to the cantilever to assure adequate contact between the microsphere and TM. Nanometer displacements were then applied to the cantilever to generate nano-indentations at audio frequencies (Figure 3 right). Results were analyzed to determine the magnitude and phase of the force by which the TM resisted indentation.

FIGURE 3. Dynamic nanoscale indentations of the TM. Left panel: A microsphere ($0.75 \mu\text{m}$ radius) is rigidly attached to an AFM cantilever so that nanometer displacements of the cantilever indent the TM. The resulting force on the TM is determined from the bending of the cantilever, so that the complex-valued dynamic stiffness can be computed as the ratio of force from the cantilever to TM indentation. Right panel: Schematic illustration of temporal pattern of TM indentation. The TM is statically indented ($\delta_0 = 0.1-0.4 \mu\text{m}$) and then dynamically indented by a pseudorandom sequence of nanometer displacement steps at audio frequencies (bottom trace). The frequency dependence of the resulting forces (top trace) is determined using a Fourier transform.

RESULTS

To characterize the force exerted by the TM on structures as small as a single hair bundle or single stereocilium, we measured the magnitude and phase of the dynamic indentation modulus E^* using the microsphere method. To characterize effects of loss of Ceacam16, we compared results for TMs from *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} and wild-type mice. To investigate possible spatial variations associated with holes seen in *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} TMs (as illustrated in the right panel Figure 1), we repeated measurements at a number of different measurement sites in each TM. To characterize effects of probe size, we also measured indentation moduli using microspheres with two different radii.

Magnitude of the dynamic indentation modulus. Measurements of the magnitude $|E^*|$ are shown in Figure 4 for typical apical portions of a wild-type TM (red) and a *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} TM (black) at several different indentation sites. All of the measured magnitudes increase gradually with frequency, rising by about a factor of 10 as frequency increases from 1 Hz to 3 kHz. Measured magnitudes for wild-type TMs were larger for basal segments of the TM than for apical segments by approximately a factor of 10. While measured magnitudes for *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} TMs were also a bit larger for basal segments, the base-to-apex differences were smaller for these mutants than for wild types. Lack of Ceacam16 reduced $|E^*|$ at all measured frequencies, however the effect was more pronounced at the base, where $|E^*|$ was more significantly reduced.

Phase of the dynamic indentation modulus. While there are large differences in the magnitudes of E^* measured in *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} and wild-type TMs, the phases are not significantly different (Figure 5). This is surprising given the large holes that are seen in the ultrastructure of the *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} TMs. This result suggests that both the stiffness and viscosity of the *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} and wild-type matrices are reduced while their ratio remains nearly constant. Perhaps the lack of Ceacam16 reduces the amount but not the poroelastic properties of the TM matrix – at least in the vicinity of the outer hair cell bundles.

Effect of probe size. For viscoelastic materials, dissipation of energy is independent of length scale. In contrast, dissipation due to flow-dependent poroelasticity depends on the length scale of fluid flow through the poroelastic

FIGURE 4. Dynamic nanoindentation responses of the TM. Magnitude $|E^*|$ of the dynamic indentation modulus as a function of indentation frequency for apical (top) and basal (bottom) segments of the TMs of wild-type (red curve) and $Ceacam16^{\beta gal/\beta gal}$ (black curve) TMs. The mean and 95% confidence interval (shaded area) are based on $n = 2$ indentation locations on a typical wild-type TM preparation and $n = 5$ different indentation locations on a typical $Ceacam16^{\beta gal/\beta gal}$ TM preparation.

FIGURE 5. Phase $\angle E^*$ of dynamic nanoindentation modulus as a function of indentation frequency for $Ceacam16^{\beta gal/\beta gal}$ (black curve) and wild-type (red curve) TMs. The mean and 95% confidence interval (shaded area) are based on $n = 2$ indentation locations on a typical wild-type TM preparation and $n = 5$ different indentation locations on a typical $Ceacam16^{\beta gal/\beta gal}$ TM preparation. At low and high frequencies, the phase angle of the dynamic indentation response approaches zero, while near the transition frequency the phase angle approaches $\pi/2$.

matrix. Thus, varying the amount of fluid moved through pores of the TM by varying the stimulation tip size or indentation depth should alter the nanoindentation response of the TM as a function of frequency. According to linear poroelasticity theory (Grodzinsky, 2011, Nia *et al.*, 2011), the peak frequency f_{peak} is proportional to the product of the equilibrium modulus E and the hydraulic permeability k of a poroelastic material, and is inversely proportional to the contact distance d between the AFM tip and the material (where d is calculated from the contact geometry as $d = 2R \cos^{-1}[(R - \delta_0)/R]$) (Figure 3):

$$f_{peak} \propto \frac{kE}{d^2} \quad (1)$$

Thus, probing the dependence of f_{peak} with the length scale of indentation d provides a method to determine if solid-fluid interactions underlie the dynamic nanomechanical measurements versus that of a purely solid-phase viscoelastic material, which would not vary with contact distance. We performed this test on apical region wild-type and $Ceacam16^{\beta gal/\beta gal}$ TMs using $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $15 \mu\text{m}$ diameter colloidal probe tips. For apical to middle region TMs, using a probe tip size of $15 \mu\text{m}$ shifted the peak frequency to ~ 1 Hz from higher frequencies observed with the $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ tip (Figure 6). This shift in f_{peak} to lower frequencies with an increase in probe tip size confirms predictions from Eq.

1, supporting the poroelastic basis of material properties of the *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} and *Ceacam16*^{+/+} TMs.

FIGURE 6. Dependence of nanoindentation response of *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} TMs on size of probe. Increasing probe tip size from a diameter of 1.5 μ m to 15 μ m decreased f_{peak} from \sim 300 Hz ($n = 5$ indentation sites) to \sim 1 Hz ($n = 3$ indentation sites) for two separate apical TM preparations.

SUMMARY

In this manuscript, we have applied a nanoindentation method to measure the dynamic moduli of TMs from *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} and wild-type mice. Results show that the magnitude of the dynamic modulus of TMs from adult *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} mice tends to be smaller than that of TMs from wild-type mice (Figure 4), which is similar to results from previous measurements based on TM waves. Despite these large differences in magnitude, the phases of the complex modulus were strikingly similar – which can only happen if the lack of *Ceacam16* gave rise to proportional differences in the elastic and viscous components of the complex modulus.

Nanoindentation measurements demonstrate a strong dependence of phase on the size of the measurement probe. Decreasing the diameter of the microsphere (Figure 3) by a factor of 10 decreased the peak frequency of the phase measurement by a factor of approximately 150 (Figure 6), which is in good agreement with the factor of 100 change that is predicted by linear poroelasticity theory. This result further supports the idea that the TMs of both *Ceacam16* ^{β gal/ β gal} and wild-type mice behave much more like poroelastic solids than viscoelastic solids.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[George Burwood]: Nice method! It is a convincing observation to find the mechanical property differences more pronounced at the base than the apex - if memory serves the initial description of the TM phenotype in this mouse indicated more severe changes to the basal TM over the apical. Is there a representative micrograph to show the morphology of the apical, middle and basal turns?

[Dennis Freeman]: Figure 3 in Cheatham et al. (2014) shows toluidine-blue-stained semithin sections from TMs of wild-type, heterozygous, and homozygous mice at P43. That same figure shows percent of TM profile occupied by holes. For the homozygous case (which we reported in the present study), the percent occupied by holes was approximately 29% at the 4 kHz place, 19% at the 8 kHz place, and 8% at the 20 kHz place, and 4% at the 40 kHz place. While the prominence of holes was greater in the apex, we measured a bigger effect on dynamic modulus in the adult base than in the adult apex.

[George Burwood]: Are the TM samples measured in artificial endolymph?

[Dennis Freeman]: Yes. The perfusate in the present study was artificial endolymph, prepared as described in Mansour, et al. (2021): 174 mM KCl, 5 mM HEPES, 3 mM dextrose, 2 mM NaCl, and 0.02 mM CaCl₂. This solution was then equilibrated at room temperature to pH 7.15 using 0.1 M HCl.

[George Burwood]: Is AFM limited to such low frequencies?

[Dennis Freeman]: Measurements in the present study were limited to frequencies less than 3 kHz by our AFM. We are currently developing a closely related system that uses a Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV) as the detector instead of the AFM. The LDV should allow measurements over a larger range of frequencies.

[George Burwood]: Can you comment on the choice to use up to 3 kHz to test the mechanical properties of TM samples whose location would be associated to BFs in the tens of kHz? For your tests of the Basal TM pieces, there appears to be a relatively stable difference between the two groups in 2C, but at the highest frequencies this difference seems to diverge. Would it be valuable/practical to extend the frequency range of the measurements?

[Dennis Freeman]: We agree that extending the high-frequency limits of our method would be useful. Our current system was quite adequate for measuring with a 15 μm microsphere, and just barely adequate for measuring with a 1.5 μm microsphere (Figure 6). If the bandwidth of our system were increased to the tens of kilohertz range, then we could use probes with sub-micrometer radii, which would more directly test the importance of poroelasticity to both high frequency stimuli and interactions of the TM with individual stereocilia.

[Lauren Chiriboga]: Where on the TM are these nanoindentations being made? Are they in the direction of the striations of the Ceacam16 mice?

[Dennis Freeman]: We used a cell adhesive (Cell-Tak) to fasten the covernet surface of a section of the TM to a small square of glass cut from a coverslip. The AFM probe was brought into contact with the surface of the TM that normally faces the reticular lamina, and it was vibrated perpendicular to that surface (i.e., in a transverse direction). These vibrations are perpendicular to the direction of the radial collagen fibers of the TM, which are thought to be oriented in the direction of sound induced motions.

[Lauren Chiriboga]: Were there differences based on the amount of static displacement of the cantilever? I would figure it would change the length scale of the indentation.

[Dennis Freeman]: As you suggest, the method presented here for measuring dynamic stiffness is sensitive to static displacement. To set the static displacement, we slowly decreased the distance between the AFM probe and the surface of the TM while monitoring motions of the AFM tip. When motions were detected, we then advanced the probe by an additional amount equal to the radius of the microsphere. Errors in the accuracy of this placement probably account for some of the variability seen in Figures 4 and 5.

[Lauren Chiriboga]: Is there a difference between heterozygous and homozygous Ceacam16 affecting the degree of manipulation of the matrix?

[Dennis Freeman]: We did not measure TMs from heterozygous mice, but it seems likely that there would be important differences between heterozygotes and homozygotes based on morphological differences that have been

previously reported Cheatham, et al. (2014).

[Wei-Ching Lin]: Re. “spatial scales on the order of single hair bundles,” could you be more specific? Say, diameter of 1.5 μm representing typical bundle height. I suppose the dimension was to approximate either the thickness of the first-row outer hair cell stereocilia (0.2-0.3 μm) or the bundle height (2-4 μm).

[Dennis Freeman]: The size of the indenter plays an important role in determining the material properties of a poroelastic solid because it determines where the velocities of the interstitial fluid and matrix differ significantly and where they do not. Because the shape of a hair bundle is complicated, it’s difficult to attribute an effective spherical radius to any particular feature of a hair bundle. However, the smallest meaningful dimension of an isolated hair bundle is perhaps the width of a single stereocilium since it would be difficult to imagine a hair bundle generating a flow profile with smaller diameter. Similarly, the largest meaningful dimension of an isolated hair bundle is perhaps the diameter of an entire bundle. Based on these types of arguments, we chose an equivalent radius of 1.5 μm , which falls between these two limits.

[Wei-Ching Lin]: Re. ‘normalized shear viscosity’, I could not find by which quantity the viscosity was normalized. The reader might want to understand the physical unit of um^2 .

[Dennis Freeman]: The normalized shear viscosity shown in Figure 2 was normalized by $\rho\omega$ where ρ is the density of TM (which was taken to be equal to that of water) and ω is radian frequency. A more detailed description of this relation is given in Mansour, et al. (2021).